

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Dataset of near-bottom sensors on SAMBA array

Deliverable D5.3

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1. Publishable summary

In this deliverable, we present a consolidated set of upper- and bottom-ocean observational datasets spanning the South Atlantic (45°S–0°N), with a particular focus on the SAMBA array and its broader regional context. The dataset brings together seven observational subsets, including hydrographic profiles from the SAMBA-MSM60, SAMBA-West, and GO-SHIP A09 and A10 cruises, GoodHope cruises, individual Argo temperature and salinity profiles, and two monthly gridded products based on the IAP and SIO-Argo data. The dataset covers essential ocean variables — temperature, salinity, and dissolved oxygen — and provides a basin-scale view of ocean conditions across the full water column. All component datasets have undergone established calibration and quality-control procedures, and comparisons among independent data sources demonstrate consistent representation of key upper-ocean physical properties.

Originally, this deliverable was intended to focus primarily on newly deployed near-bottom sensors on the deepest SAMBA moorings. However, delays in deploying and recovering part of the mooring array necessitated a change in scope. As a result, the deliverable has been expanded to provide a broader observational dataset integrating both near-bottom measurements and upper-ocean products across the South Atlantic. By reducing observational gaps and providing openly accessible, quality-controlled data, this deliverable supports research on long-term ocean change, improves the evaluation of climate and ocean models, and contributes to international observing and assessment efforts.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Description of Dataset

In total, seven observational subsets were collected across the South Atlantic Basin (45°S–0°N), comprising five cruise/float individual profile datasets and two gridded datasets (Tan et al., 2026). The key ocean variables included are temperature and salinity, followed by dissolved oxygen.

Specifically:

(1) Cruise/float individual profile datasets

- SAMBA-MSM60 cruises
- SAMBA-West (SAM02-SAM18) cruises
- GO-SHIP A09 and A10 cruises
- South Atlantic individual Argo profiles
- GoodHope cruises

(2) Gridded products

- South Atlantic IAP monthly gridded products (0-6000 m)
- South Atlantic SIO-Argo monthly gridded products (0-2000 m)

The complete list of subsets is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of upper- and bottom-ocean observational datasets from the SAMBA array to the South Atlantic, including variables, spatial coverage, temporal coverage, and data type, etc

Order	Dataset name	Folder name	Filename	Variable	Spatial coverage	Temporal coverage	Type	References	Comments
1	SAMBA-MSM60	/SAMBA-MSM60	mism_060_1_ctd_<station>.nc	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), dissolved oxygen (umol/kg), pressure (dbar)	34.5S; surface-bottom	January, 2017	Cruises	Karstensen et al., 2019	netCDF format
2	SAMBA-West	/SAMBA-West	CTD_SAM_<cruises_order>.mat	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), dissolved oxygen (umol/kg), pressure (dbar) potential density (kg/m3)	34.5S (47W-51W); surface-bottom	2010-2017	Cruises	Meinen et al., 2020	SAM02-SAM18; Matlab format SAM06, SAM09, SAM11, SAM17 are not available
3	GO-SHIP A09, A10 cruises	/GO-SHIP	GOSHIP_A09_2009.mat GOSHIP_A09_2018.mat GOSHIP_A10_2011.mat	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), Depth (meters)	A09 (24S; 45W-15E) A10 (30S; 48W-15E) surface-bottom	2009, 2011, 2018	Cruises	Katsumata et al., 2022	Matlab format
4	South Atlantic Individual Argo profiles	/Argo_T_S_float	Argo_SA_2005_2023.mat	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), Depth (meters)	45S~0 ; 70W~25E surface-bottom	2005-2023	Float	Argo 2020	Matlab format
5	GoodHope (GH) cruises	/GoodHope	GoodHope_2004_CTD_profile_Russia_AK_S_V AVILOV.nc GoodHope_2006_CTD_profiles_Russia_Ak_S _Vavilov.mat GoodHope_2008_CTD_profiles_MarionDufres ne.nc GoodHope_2009_CTD_profiles_SouthAfrica_S A_Agulhas.mat	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), Dissolved oxygen (umol/kg), Pressure (meters), etc.	GoodHope Transect surface-bottom	2004, 2006, 2008, 2009	Cruises	Gladyshev et al., 2008; Speich and Dehairs 2008	Matlab and NetCDF format
5	South Atlantic IAP monthly gridded products	/IAP_gridded_product	Temperature: IAPv4_Temp_monthly_1_6000m_year_<year> _month_<month>_SouthAtlantic.nc Salinity: IAPv2_Salinity_monthly_1_6000m_year_<year> _month_<month>_SouthAtlantic.nc	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), Standard Depth (meters)	45S~0 ; 70W~25E 1 degree; 0-6000 meters with 119 standard depth level	1960-2024	Grid	Cheng et al., 2020, 2024	netCDF format
6	South Atlantic SIO Argo gridded product	/SIO-Argo	Temperature: ARGO_TEMPERATURE_<year><month>.nc Salinity: ARGO_SALINITY_<year><month>.nc	temperature (oC), salinity (psu), Standard Pressure (dbar)	45S~0 ; 70W~25E 1 degree; 2.5-1975 dbar with 58 standard pressure level	2004-2024	Grid	Roemmich and Gilson 2009	netCDF format

2.1.2 Data processing techniques

(1) SAMBA-MSM60 cruise

The MSM60 hydrographic profiles were collected during the MSM60 cruise (R/V Maria S. Merian) along the nominal 34.5°S transect in January 2017 (Karstensen et al., 2019), with stations spaced at approximately 50 km intervals and extending from the surface to the seafloor. At each station, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and pressure were measured using a pumped Sea-Bird SBE 9plus CTD system. The dataset underwent expert manual quality control, including removal of outliers and calibration adjustments.

(2) SAMBA-west (SAM02-SAM18) cruises

The SAMBA-West hydrographic profiles were collected between 2010 and 2017 along the western boundary line near 34.5°S during the SAM cruises (SAM02-SAM18), conducted primarily on Argentine vessels supported by the Servicio de Hidrografía Naval, such as R/V Puerto Deseado and ARA Austral, with NOAA/AOML participation (Meinen et al., 2020). The cruises combined PIES/CPIES servicing and acoustic telemetry with repeat CTD (and sometimes LADCP) hydrographic sections along the mooring line and onto the shelf. Quality control followed standard shipboard CTD workflows. Observations were calibrated using pre- and post-cruise factory calibration (SBE 9plus) where available; where not available, conductivity sensors were calibrated against salinity samples measured with an Autosal salinometer, standardised with OSIL SSW. Where oxygen samples were collected, SBE43 oxygen sensors were calibrated against Winkler-method measurements. Post-processing quality control was also performed manually to remove questionable observations.

(3) GO-SHIP A09 and A10 cruises

Temperature and salinity hydrographic profiles were collected from two GO-SHIP sections: A09 at 24°S, occupied in March 2009 and March-April 2018, and A10 at 30°S, occupied in October 2011 from the GO-SHIP Easy Ocean product (Katsumata et al., 2022). All profiles were subjected to rigorous manual quality control, including CTD calibration and removal of anomalous measurements.

(4) South Atlantic individual Argo profiles

The dataset incorporates individual Argo temperature and salinity profiles from the South Atlantic, sourced from the Argo Global Data Assembly Centre (GDAC). The profiles were processed and formatted by the CAS Oceanographic Data Centre, Global Ocean Science Database (CODC), and have undergone standard Argo quality control and bias correction procedures (Argo 2020), with additional quality control applied by the CODC. Floats listed on the Argo grey list were excluded. In total, 120,518 temperature and salinity profiles collected between 2005 and 2023, within the region 0°-45°S, 65°W-20°E, were compiled.

(5) GoodHope (GH) cruises

Temperature, salinity, and dissolved oxygen CTD hydrographic profiles from the GoodHope sections were collected from three research vessels: RV Akademik Sergey Vavilov (Russia, in 2004 and 2006), RV Marion Dufresne (France, in 2008), and S.A. Agulhas (South Africa, in 2009) (Speich and Dehairs 2008; Gladyshev et al., 2008). All profiles were subjected to rigorous manual quality control, including CTD calibration and removal of anomalous measurements.

(6) South Atlantic IAP temperature and salinity gridded products (0-6000m)

The monthly IAP (Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences) global temperature gridded product (Version 4.1) and global salinity gridded product (Version 2.1) have a horizontal resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ for the upper 6000 m across 119 standard depth levels (Cheng et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2024). Data processing includes an enhanced automatic quality-control system that accounts for local temperature and salinity distribution skewness, topographic barriers, and climate-driven shifts in water-mass properties; bias corrections for in situ temperature measurements (XBTs, MBTs, bottle data, and Argo profiling buoys); and a gap-filling ensemble optimal interpolation (EnOI) approach that applies dynamic covariances to sampling errors arising from heterogeneous temporal and spatial observation density.

(7) South Atlantic SIO-Argo gridded product (0-2000m)

The SIO/Scripps Argo monthly temperature and salinity fields (Roemmich-Gilson Argo Climatology; Roemmich and Gilson 2009) are available at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution from 2004 to 2024 and are based exclusively on quality-controlled Argo profiling floats. Data production involves a local weighted least-squares fit to the nearest 100 Argo profiles within each month to estimate the background mean field, followed by an optimal estimation step applied to the anomaly field (Roemmich and Gilson 2009), with a modification of the zonal equatorial correlation scale used in the optimal estimation. The SIO-Argo product was not affected by the salinity drift that impacted certain Argo datasets after 2016.

Figure 1 shows a comparison of both gridded products with ship-based CTD data. The results indicate that both IAP and SIO-Argo capture the core thermohaline structure of Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) without producing spurious spikes or abrupt shifts. Because gridded products are constructed from monthly atlases that blend neighbouring observations, transect-scale variability appears smoother relative to individual cruise measurements. The root-mean-square errors (RMSE) for both gridded products relative to benchmark profiles are near zero, indicating high fidelity in reproducing AAIW core properties. Additional validation against individual Argo profiles after 2005 (Fig. 1e-f) reveals strong positive correlations between IAP estimates and Argo-derived salinity minimum (S_{min}) and temperature at S_{min} , with most comparisons aligning closely along the one-to-one line.

These comparisons demonstrate that both gridded products (IAP and SIO-Argo) are in good agreement with ship-based and individual Argo float data, reliably capturing the thermal and saline characteristics of core AAIW in the South Atlantic without introducing systematic biases. This confirms that the upper-ocean water masses of the South Atlantic are well represented, including Surface Water (SW; 0-200 m), South Atlantic Central Water (SACW; 200-600 m), and Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW; 600-1200 m).

Fig.1: Validation of upper-ocean observational datasets in the South Atlantic. Validation is shown for the intermediate layer, represented by core AAIW properties at the salinity minimum: salinity minimum (Smin), temperature at Smin, and neutral density at Smin. Datasets shown include the GO-SHIP A09 and A10 cruises, SAMBA-MSM60, South Atlantic individual Argo profiles, South Atlantic IAP monthly gridded products, and the South Atlantic SIO-Argo gridded product. (a) Along-track comparison along the GO-SHIP A09 line (March-April 2009, 24°S). (b-c) Same as (a), but along the GO-SHIP A10 line (October 2011, 30°S) and the MSM60 line (January 2017, 34.5°S). Shaded envelopes denote the 95% confidence interval of the IAP estimates, incorporating instrumental, sampling, and mapping uncertainties. Root-mean-square errors (RMSEs) for each comparison are reported. (d-f) Scatterplot comparisons between IAP atlas estimates (x-axis) and individual Argo float measurements (y-axis), with point colour indicating latitude.

2.1.3 Deviations from the original plan

Originally, D5.3 was planned to complement water-column studies by adding near-bottom sensors to the deepest SAMBA moorings, using data collected over the preceding 15 years, to record high-frequency salinity variations in the abyssal layer. To this end, new sensors (MicroCATs) were purchased and delivered to our international partners in South Africa (DEFF) and Argentina (SHN) for deployment on the eastern and western abyssal plains of the SAMBA array. The sensors delivered to South Africa (SAMBA-East) were

anchored to two PIES moorings and successfully deployed in the Cape Basin in September 2023. The sensors delivered to Argentina (SAMBA-West) were eventually deployed in June 2025 by a Brazilian Navy vessel, following the cancellation of the original Argentine partner cruise due to funding cuts by the new Argentine government (Speich 2025).

The SAMBA-East MicroCats were scheduled for recovery in October 2025. However, due to an unforeseen incident, the research vessel initially scheduled to depart in October 2025 was forced to return to port shortly after departure because of a hull breach. As a result, the recovery of the instruments has been postponed; they are now scheduled for recovery in October 2026 and will become available shortly thereafter, following calibration and validation. This timeline extends beyond the close of the OCEAN ICE project. The broader impact on the project is nevertheless expected to be limited, and no major knock-on effects are anticipated.

As a mitigation measure, we have shifted the scientific focus from the abyssal data originally expected from the SAMBA Eastern and Western arrays to the broader South Atlantic water column, spanning from the surface down to 2000 m, with particular attention to the Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW), which represents the upper limb of the AMOC. To support this expanded scope, GO-SHIP data and additional gridded atlas products have been incorporated alongside the existing SAMBA hydrographic data, building on methodologies that have successfully separated anthropogenic warming and salinity changes in the upper ocean. Accordingly, D5.3 now provides a consolidated set of upper- and deep-ocean observational datasets (0-6000 m) from the SAMBA array and the broader South Atlantic (45°S-0°N), integrating both the available near-bottom measurements and the expanded upper-ocean products described above.

2.2 References

Zhetao Tan, Sabrina Speich, and Elaine McDonagh (2026): Upper and Bottom Ocean Observational Datasets from the SAMBA Array to the Broader South Atlantic (OCEAN ICE; Dataset). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/uploads/19455472>

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J. Karstensen et al., Seamount Observatory and SAMOC Overturning, Cruise No. MSM60, January 04-February 01, 2017, Cape Town (South Africa)-Montevideo (Uruguay). (2019).

Meinen, Christopher S., et al. Observed ocean bottom temperature variability at four sites in the northwestern Argentine Basin: Evidence of decadal deep/abyssal warming amidst hourly to interannual variability during 2009–2019. *Geophysical Research Letters* 47.18 (2020): e2020GL089093.

Gladyshev, S., M. Arhan, A. Sokov, and S. Speich (2008), A hydrographic section from South Africa to the southern limit of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current at the Greenwich meridian, *Deep Sea Res., Part I*, 55(10), 1284–1303.

Speich, S. and Dehairs, F. (2008), Cruise Report, MD 166 / BONUS-GOODHOPE. <https://campagnes.flotteoceanographique.fr/campagnes/8200030/>

2.3 Open Science

The open-access dataset underlying this deliverable is deposited in the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/19455472>) as open access, with tags pointing to OCEAN ICE. The citation is: Zhetao Tan, Sabrina Speich, and Elaine McDonagh (2026): Upper and Bottom Ocean Observational Datasets from the SAMBA Array to the Broader South Atlantic (OCEAN ICE; Dataset). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/uploads/19455472>

Two peer-reviewed publications are directly relevant to D5.3.

- Tan, Z., von Schuckmann, K., Speich, S. et al. Observed large-scale and deep-reaching compound ocean state changes over the past 60 years. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 16, 58-68 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02484-x>. This paper is published open access in Nature Climate Change under a CC BY licence, with no embargo period. The Version of Record has been deposited in the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/17725659>) under a CC BY licence.
- The manuscript entitled "Four Decades of Upper-Ocean Water Mass Changes in the South Atlantic Under a Warming Climate" by Zhetao Tan, Sabrina Speich, Elaine McDonagh, Artémis Zegna Rata and Gaston Manta, currently under review at Science Advances. The authors have selected a CC BY licence; the paper will be published open access with no embargo period.

At the Ocean Sciences Meeting 2026 (February 2026, Glasgow), project member Zhetao Tan, lead author of the D5.3 draft, presented the latest findings on long-term water mass changes in the South Atlantic, using the D5.3 dataset (<https://ocean-ice.eu/ocean-ice-presentations-at-ocean-science-meeting-2026-glasgow/>). Drawing on direct observations, the presentation elucidated the physical processes driving changes in compound temperature and salinity in response to global warming, from a water-mass perspective. The presentation also called attention to ongoing climate transformations in the Global South, arguing that these should be given equal prominence to those in the Global North within the ocean science community

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This dataset extends South Atlantic observational coverage from individual transects to the broader basin scale, supporting the study of ocean state evolution since the 1960s across the full water column. In particular, it enables assessment of changes in the characteristics (temperature, salinity, volume, and density) of the main water masses (e.g., AAIW, CDW, SACW, AABW) and the mechanisms governing their formation and export pathways around Antarctica. This contribution is developed within the framework of WP5.

O2: Support model: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

This dataset supports Southern Ocean and South Atlantic Ocean model development, including simulations of vertical and horizontal mixing, ocean heat transport, and the formation and export of bottom water from the Weddell Sea to the South Atlantic basin. These observational constraints will inform improvements in coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-climate models.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

Data consolidation and delivery will be achieved through close integration with SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus data delivery services, in accordance with FAIR principles and INSPIRE. The publication highlighted in this deliverable (Tan et al., 2026, Nature Climate Change) will support the upcoming IPCC-AR7 assessment, particularly contributing to WGI Chapter 2 (Large-scale changes in the climate system and their causes) and WGI Chapter 4 (Advances in process understanding of Earth system changes). This dataset will also support engagement with key international initiatives, including SOOS, SAMOC, and the EU Polar Cluster.